

GGOS DOI Committee

Metadata Recommendations for geodetic data: GNSS

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Metadata Recommendations for Geodetic data: GNSS

GGOS Committee on Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) for Geodetic Data Sets

Version 30 August 2025

Abstract

Data publications with digital object identifiers (DOI) are key supporting elements for Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) data (Wilkinson et al. 2016). DOIs were originally developed to provide permanent access to static datasets described in scholarly literature. Currently, they are increasingly being used for both static and dynamic data. DOIs are providing globally unique, persistent and resolvable references of various types of sources (data, software, samples, equipment) and means of rewarding the originators and institutions (through citation). This is important for geodesy, as researchers rely on observational data and operational aspects. Geodetic equipment, observational data and results require a documented mechanism for citation, scientific recognition and reward that can be provided by assigning a DOI.

To address these challenges and identify opportunities for improved coordination and advocacy within the geodetic community, GGOS established a Working Group on 'Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) for Geodetic Datasets' in 2019, transforming it into a GGOS Committee in 2023. This Committee is designated to establish best practices and advocate for the consistent implementation of DOIs across all IAG Services and in the greater geodetic community.

This document presents the GGOS DOI Committee's first set of recommendations for DOI metadata for geodetic data. These recommendations have been developed for GNSS data and include specific guidance on different GNSS data products. However, many sections of this document are not specific to GNSS data and may also be applicable to other geodetic data.

Citation

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1. Introduction and background

Data publications with digital object identifiers (DOI) are key supporting elements for Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) data (Wilkinson et al. 2016). DOIs were originally developed to provide permanent access to static datasets described in scholarly literature. Currently, they are increasingly being used for both static and dynamic data. DOIs are providing globally unique, persistent and resolvable references of various types of sources (data, software, samples, equipment) and means of rewarding the originators and institutions (through citation). As a result of international groups, like the Coalition on Publishing Data in the Earth, Space and Environmental Sciences (COPDESS) and the Enabling FAIR Data project (both at <https://copdess.org>), data with assigned DOIs are fully citable in scholarly literature. In addition, an increasing number of scientific journals require data, software and other sources underlying the results described in a publication to be available – even before accepting an article. Initial metrics for data citation allows data providers to demonstrate the value of the data collected by institutes and individual scientists.

The DOI system is governed by an international, non-for-profit organization, the International DOI Foundation (IDF, <https://www.doi.org/>) that manages DOI registries and provides services to the community (e.g., DOI-resolving services). IDF Members are DOI registration agencies that provide additional services for their communities, including DOI registration services. The first DOI registration agency, Crossref (<https://crossref.org/>), was founded already in 2000, when the DOI was “invented” to provide persistent online access to online versions of scholarly literature and research articles. Until today, most publishers are registering their DOIs through Crossref. DataCite (<https://datacite.org/>) was founded in 2009 with the original purpose to provide DOI for data and “grey literature”. Today, both agencies are important players in making all kinds of research objects easy to find, cite, link, assess, and reuse jointly develop tools to connect data with the literature (e.g., Event Data). DOIs can be registered by members of the DOI registration agencies. Individual institutions can become members or join an existing (DataCite) consortium if they wish to register/mint DOIs.

1.1. DOI Metadata

For the registration of a DOI, the provision of at least a minimum of descriptive metadata is required (mainly bibliographic information, see below for details). These must be provided to the DOI registration agency in specific, machine-actionable formats (originally XML, now also JSON) following the dedicated metadata schema of the respective DOI registration agency (e.g., <https://schema.datacite.org/> for DataCite).

Since its foundation, DataCite focused on the DOI assignment for research data and, consequently, their metadata schema (current version: v. 4.6) has been and is continuously further developed (by the DataCite Metadata Working Group) to be suitable and appropriate for the identification and discovery of research data. Individual data centres need to look at the (mostly minor) changes between versions before they implement their workflows. The examples in this document are valid for DataCite Metadata Schema 4.6.

The metadata recommendations detailed in this document focus on the DataCite Metadata properties and their application for geodetic datasets. The recommendations further provide examples of the community standards for geodetic stations (site logs and GeodesyML) and on how to map information between these and the DataCite metadata. A lookup table (Appendix) provides examples for different GNSS data products). They have been developed within the “GGOS Committee on Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) for Geodetic Data Sets” (<https://ggos.org/about/org/co/dois-geodetic-data-sets/>) and the IGS Governing Board.

The DataCite Metadata Schema is categorized into **mandatory**, **recommended** and **optional** properties. **Mandatory** elements must be provided for all DOIs and mainly include the elements to enable the citation of the object identified with the DOI and the resource type (see below for detailed recommendations):

1. **Identifier:** the DOI code; i.e., a prefix and suffix separated by a forward slash (e.g., 10.5880/GFZ.1.1.2020.002). The prefix identifies the DOI minting agency/ repository (here GFZ Data Services) and the suffix can be freely created. Suffixes may be random codes (numbers and letters) or include semantic elements. The discussion about advantages or disadvantages for either option is not within the scope of these recommendations.
2. **Creator/s:** similar to authors for articles, creators can be personal or institutional). Creators are included in the citation of the dataset (in contrast to contributors).
3. **Title** (the title of a dataset is an important element for data discovery and shall briefly describe the content of the data)
4. **Publication year:** this can either be the year when the data DOI was minted, or the year when the data was made available on the internet, or the year when, e.g., a continuous measurement began. For GNSS station data, we recommend to use the start date of the first receiver entry in the site log
5. **Publisher:** the DOI minting organization/ institution or repository
6. **Resource type with (ResourceTypeGeneral):** the object type, e.g., dataset, collection, book, journal article, instrument, physical object (controlled list). For GNSS data, data products and networks, the ResourceTypeGeneral should be “dataset”.

In addition, the DataCite Metadata Working Group strongly encourages DOI minting agencies that “**wish to enhance the prospects that their metadata will be found, cited, and linked to original research [..], to submit both the Recommended and Mandatory sets of properties.** Together, the Mandatory and Recommended sets of properties and their sub-properties are especially valuable to information seekers and added-service providers, such as indexers. The Metadata Working Group members strongly urge the inclusion of metadata identified as Recommended for the purpose of achieving greater exposure for the resource’s metadata record and, therefore, the underlying research itself.” (DataCite Metadata Working Group, 2024).

Important sub-properties for interlinking research outcome/products in machine-readable way are persistent identifiers (PID) that uniquely identify persons (ORCID), institutions (ROR), funding agencies (ROR, FundRef), related references (articles, datasets, samples via DOI). They are key supporting elements for FAIR data and should be considered also for GeodesyML files or site logs. In addition, it is further possible to include controlled vocabulary lists with information on their schema and unique value (according to the SKOS guidelines) in the DataCite `Subjects` property (= keywords).

1.2. Challenges for assigning DOI for geodetic datasets: the case of GNSS datasets

Most geodetic datasets are dynamic, i.e., changing over time. Typical GNSS data products are time series of station positions and velocities, satellite-derived orbits and clocks, precipitable water vapor, etc. The following recommendations have been developed for GNSS data, but represent a blueprint for other geodetic data products. Most examples in this document are for observational data originating from GNSS ground stations. The DOI recommendations for geodetic/ GNSS data shall not replace the DataCite Schema documentation, but recommend specific metadata elements that are appropriate for geodetic data based on community agreements and support the provision of harmonised metadata for GNSS data. The aim is further to align the DOI metadata with existing, disciplinary metadata standard e.g., IGS site logs or GeodesyML files for GNSS ground stations and support automated metadata mapping between existing GNSS ground station metadata and the DataCite Schema.

Compared to seismological data, GNSS data are similarly dynamic and similarly standardized, but without a central governance and clear network structure which makes the DOI assignment for GNSS data more challenging. Seismic networks are centrally governed by the Federation of Digital Seismic Networks (FDSN) and promote the use of DOI for seismic networks for all passive seismological investigations (International Federation of Digital Seismic Networks, 2014, updated 2023). Each network is assigned an individual network code (provided by FDSN) and operated by one group/ institution. These seismic network DOIs are not meant to uniquely identify individual data streams, but provide citation (and credit) for the group or institution operating and managing these seismic networks (Evans et al., 2015). This central governance is missing for GNSS data: GNSS datasets originate from a very large number of GNSS ground stations, organized in global, regional, or local networks where one GNSS station can even contribute to different networks. Some institutions organize their GNSS station/s as networks others don't. An existing GNSS network could be the highest level of granularity for a DOI. If no networks exist, we would need to assign DOIs to the data for each individual GNSS station that can later be part of one or several networks. The connection of each station with one or several networks would then be possible via the “related Identifier” property of the DataCite Schema (see Figure 1). In any case: we recommend the assignment of station specific DOI only when necessary. If a network operator is able to group a number of GNSS stations under the same dataset DOI (network DOI), then this should be preferable.

Figure 1: Visualisation of the combination of several GNSS stations data (with DOI) to network. DOIs will be assigned to the continuously recorded data for each GNSS station (left). As a second step, individual stations can be grouped as GNSS networks using the “related Identifier” property of the DataCite Metadata Schema (right)

The large number of GNSS stations requires automated workflows between existing GNSS metadata databases, like M³G, the NSF GAGE Facility/EarthScope (formerly UNAVCO), etc., and the DOI registration process directly from the metadata databases or via a partner repository with only minor provision of additional information. We therefore recommend the integration of persistent identifiers (ROR, ORCID) also in these metadata databases and consider also to add links to relevant documents (e.g., RINEX format description) or articles to the station metadata (if possible).

For derived GNSS Data Products, like IGS orbit/clock or reprocessing products, calculated by different IGS Analysis Centres (using data measured at many stations), we recommend to use DOIs for the products (e.g., rapid or final IGS products, multi GNSS products). Similar to the GNSS station examples, derived GNSS data products might also require different levels of granularity (i.e., solutions of individual analysis centres, combined solutions, etc).

For GNSS campaign data, one DOI can be assigned for the data of the campaign. GNSS campaign data are usually static and DOIs normally minted after the end of the campaign.

Similar to the seismological example above, most of these DOIs are for citation purposes and shall provide credit for the individuals or organization measuring and processing the data. They are not intended to identify specific data files within a GNSS station, product or campaign.

1.3. Citations of DOI-referenced data

The citation of a dataset or data product with assigned DOI looks like a “normal” citation of any other publication and includes the information provided in the Mandatory metadata properties:

Creator/s (Publication Year). Title. Version (ResourceType General). Identifier

For example:

Männel, B.; Brandt, A.; Nischan, T.; Brack, A.; Sakic, P.; Bradke, M. (2020): GFZ final product series for the International GNSS Service (IGS)(dataset). GFZ Data Services. <https://doi.org/10.5880/GFZ.1.1.2020.002>

Consequently, a data DOI should be treated like any other source cited in a publication. It should have the citation (here “Männel et al., 2020”) in the body text of a manuscript and the full reference (in the citation style of the publisher) in the references list. Only then, automated citation analysis tool can find the data citation.

The citation recommendations/ requirements mentioned in this document, however, are referring to data publications and shall ensure a permanent digital connection between data from GNSS stations contributing to networks or combination products and thus enable credit through citation. The citation of hundreds of stations in research articles is not possible yet, but data repositories may be more flexible. Current initiatives, e.g., the Complex Data Citation Working Group of the Research Data Alliance¹ are working on solutions enabling the citation of 100+ objects in scholarly literature.

1.4. Summary of DOI minting strategies for different GNSS products

GNSS station data: we recommend to mint one DOI for the ongoing data from one GNSS station. This represents the highest DOI-granularity possible. As much as possible, metadata should be mapped from Site logs or GeodesyML files for GNSS ground stations. The DOI does not refer to individual files, but to station data for a longer period (also into the future). Data from individual stations that are part of a network need to cite the network DOI using the `relatedIdentifier` property (relation type: `IsPartOf`). Please note that we don’t generally recommend minting DOIs for GNSS station data. If an institution is organising a number of stations as a network, the network DOI may represent the highest granularity of DOIs.

GNSS Network: a network consists of several GNSS stations that are grouped according to a specific purpose. If the station data contributing to the network are assigned with DOI, each station that is part of the network needs to be cited using the `relatedIdentifier` property (relation type: `HasPart`). If the network DOI represents the highest granularity and the individual stations are not assigned with DOI, no citation is required. If a GNSS network contributes to a derived product, like, an IGS AC product, the network DOI should be treated like that of GNSS stations.

IGS AC product series (e.g., IGS ultrarapid, rapid and final solutions): one DOI for one product. All DOI of GNSS stations or networks whose data are included in the combination product need to be cited using the `relatedIdentifier` property (relation type: `IsDerivedFrom`). Please note: if ultrarapid or rapid products are not permanently archived, no DOI can be assigned.

IGS ACC combined product series: one DOI for the final products. Author: IGS, contributors: all ACs, citation of all AC solutions contributing to the final product (provided by ACs). Publisher: DOI minting agency/repository.

¹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/complex-citations-working-group/activity/>

GNSS campaigns: one DOI for all data from a GNSS campaign. Campaigns are defined as temporary installations with repeated measurements for a period. All stations and measurement points are operated by one research group and the GNSS campaign data can be regarded a static data after the end of the campaign. As such, they are different to the more complex, dynamic GNSS products described above. Normally, the researcher/s responsible for a GNSS campaign are the authors/ creators. Citations of potential GNSS station DOIs have to be considered when they are relevant for the campaign data product.

2. Recommendations for metadata properties for GNSS data in DataCite Metadata Schema

2.1. Mandatory fields

The following part describes DataCite’s mandatory and recommended metadata properties with examples for XML, GeodesyML (and site logs). A full lookup table summarising the recommendations for each data/ product type in the Appendix

DataCite DOIs must be registered with at least six mandatory elements. In addition, we recommend using several sub-properties whenever possible (including persistent identifiers, like ORCID for persons, ROR for institutions, etc.). The recommendations are also addressing existing practices by the NSF GAGE Facility/EarthScope, the Royal Belgium Observatory (ROB), and GFZ. The numbers in the headlines represent the number of metadata properties in the DataCite Metadata Schema 4.6 (DataCite Metadata Working Group 2024).

1 Identifier

The `identifier` property consists of an agent-specific DOI `prefix` (that will be provided by DataCite) plus an individually-structured DOI `suffix`. DOIs suffixes can be randomly assigned (1) or include certain semantics (2). The discussion about advantages or disadvantages for either option is not within the scope of these recommendations.

- (1) `10.7283/T5Q23XBT` (EarthScope/GAGE Example: random DOI suffix)
- (2) `10.24414/ROB-GNSS-ELIS00ATA` (ROB example: semantic DOI suffix indicating the agency [ROB], the data type [GNSS] and the station name [ELIS00ATA])[7]

2 Creator

The `creator` property contains a list of the institutions and/ or the main researcher(s) involved in operating the station or producing the data set or data product ...in priority order. DataCite creators are included in the DOI citation and are an equivalent to “authors” of articles.

For observational data from GNSS ground stations, most of the community agreed not to use individuals as creators, but institutions or agencies. These institutions are the same as in the IGS site logs /GeodesyML files and may be automatically retrieved from them. The DataCite metadata schema provides the `name-
Type` sub-properties “`Personal`” and “`Organizational`” (2.1.a). For other GNSS data (e.g. from GNSS campaigns), other GNSS products (e.g. <https://doi.org/10.5880/GFZ.1.1.2022.001>), the researchers involved in the calculation of the data are usually named as creators.

In any case, it is recommended to use as many of the following sub-properties as possible: `givenName` (2.2), `familyName` (2.3), `nameIdentifier` (2.4), `nameIdentifierScheme` (2.4.a; ORCID is recommended), `schemeURI` (2.4.b: <https://orcid.org>) `affiliation` (2.5), `affiliationIdentifier` (2.5.a), `affiliationIdentifierScheme` (2.5.b, ROR is recommended) and `schemeURI` (2.5.c: <https://ror.org>)”

for personal and organizational names. If several creators are existing, they have to be provided separately within the “creators” tag (this is already included in the examples below).

XML example for a personal name (with ORCID) and affiliation (with ROR):

```
<creators>
  <creator>
    <creatorName nameType="Personal">Bradke, Markus</creatorName>
      <givenName>Markus</givenName>
      <familyName>Bradke</familyName><nameIdentifier schemeURI=https://orcid.org/ nameIdentifierScheme="ORCID">0000-0003-1084-2909</nameIdentifier>
      <affiliation affiliationIdentifier="https://ror.org/04z8jg394" affiliationIdentifierScheme="ROR">GFZ German Research Centre for Geosciences, Potsdam, Germany</affiliation>[12]
    </creator>
</creators>
```

XML example for an organizational name with affiliation (and ROR):

```
<creators>
  <creator>
    <creatorName nameType="Organizational">Royal Observatory of Belgium</creatorName>
    <nameIdentifier schemeURI="https://ror.org/" nameIdentifierScheme="ROR">https://ror.org/00hjks330</nameIdentifier>
  </creator>
</creators>
```

3 Title

The `title` property should include appropriate elements that would help find and distinguish the data in catalogues and data portals. To support automated DOI metadata generation, we suggest combining existing information recorded in GeodesyML files or Site logs with some additional context. Appropriate elements for GNSS ground station data might include the 9-char GNSS station code, the type of station, its location and the station description. A title for a GNSS network should include the term “GNSS network” to support data discovery. An alternative could be to use the `subtitle` property. However, as this property is neither indexed in the DataCite catalogue or other portals, we don’t recommend using this option.

For example:

```
<titles>
  <title xml:lang="en">GNSS data of ELIS00ATA, Princess Elisabeth Station Antarctica</title>
</titles>
```

```
<titles>
  <title xml:lang="en">GNSS data of the global GFZ tracking network</title>
</titles>
```

In view of populating the DataCite Schema automatically, the title information could be derived from the IGS site log and the GeodesyML file:

Example from ELIS00ATA IGS site log

1. Site Identification of the GNSS Monument
Site Name: Princess Elisabeth Station Antarctica

Four Character ID: ELIS

Example from ELIS00ATA GeodesyML

```
<geo:siteIdentification>
<geo:SiteIdentification gml:id="site-identification">
<geo:siteName>Princess Elisabeth Station Antarctica</geo:siteName>
<geo:fourCharacterID>ELIS</geo:fourCharacterID>
<geo:monumentNumber>0</geo:monumentNumber>
<geo:receiverNumber>0</geo:receiverNumber>
```

Other examples for titles of GNSS stations:

- ELIS00ATA - GNSS station data, Princess Elisabeth Station, Utsteinen, Antarctica
- ROB GNSS Network Data
- Plutons GPS Network
- Plutons GPS Network (COLO-Laguna Colorada P.S.)

4 Publisher

The `publisher` property contains “the name of the entity that holds, archives, publishes prints, distributes, releases, issues, or produces the resource.” It is usually the DOI minting agency or the repository/ datacentre.

```
<publisher>Royal Observatory of Belgium</publisher> (a GNSS Data Centre)
<publisher>The NSF GAGE Facility operated by EarthScope Consortium</publisher>
(a GNSS Data Centre)
<publisher>GFZ Data Services</publisher> (a research data repository)
```

5 PublicationYear

According to the DataCite definitions, the `publicationYear` is “*The year when the data were or will be made publicly available.*” (it can be the year of the DOI registration or an earlier year if the data were accessible before). For dynamic data, DataCite recommends to use the year of the first version, which could be mapped from the installation date of the GNSS receiver.

The DataCite Metadata Schema provides the following additional guidance for the `publicationYear` property:

- If the date of public availability cannot be determined, use the date of registration.
- If an embargo period has been in effect, use the date when the embargo period ends.
- If there is no standard publication year value, use the date that would be preferred from a citation perspective.

10 ResourceType with 10.a resourceTypeGeneral

While the `resourceTypeGeneral` is a mandatory field with a controlled list, the `resourceType` property is a free text field. In this version of the metadata recommendations, we suggest to use “Dataset” as `resourceTypeGeneral` for all GNSS data and products. Future agreements with the IGS community may result in further recommendations for the `resourceType` property that will then be included in a new version of this document.

```
<resourceType resourceTypeGeneral="Dataset"> Dataset</resourceType>
<resourceType resourceTypeGeneral="Dataset"> GNSS Network</resourceType> (optional)
```

2.2. Recommendations for other properties in DataCite Metadata Schema

6 Subjects

Subjects (keywords) can be provided as free text or from controlled vocabularies with provision of the source (scheme URI, scheme value). The free-text `subject` property contains the "*subject, keyword, classification code, or key phrase describing the resource.*" Since subjects may be categorized under different schemata, the sub-properties `subjectScheme` and `schemeURI` should also be included whenever possible.

XML Example for free keywords (from <https://doi.org/10.5880/GFZ.1.1.2020.002>):

```
<subjects>
  <subject>International GNSS Service</subject>
  <subject>IGS</subject>
  <subject>IGS Analysis Centre</subject>
  <subject>IAG</subject>
  <subject>satellite orbits</subject>
  <subject>earth</subject>
  <subject>earth rotation parameters</subject>
  <subject>clock corrections</subject>
  <subject>station coordinates</subject>
  <subject>GPS</subject>
  <subject>GLONASS</subject>
</subjects>
```

In addition, we recommend using keywords from the NASA Global Change Master Directory (GCMD, <https://gcmd.earthdata.nasa.gov/KeywordViewer/>). "GCMD Keywords are a hierarchical set of controlled Earth science vocabularies that ensure Earth science data and services are described in a consistent manner". GCMD Keywords are regularly updated and provided in RDF, JSON, XML and csv formats. Among others, GCMD Keywords describe Earth Sciences in general, Earth Science Services, Instruments/Sensors, Platforms, Locations, etc. They are very powerful to describe any type of satellite-derived data and instruments, including for geodesy.

The keywords are provided with their full hierarchy and > symbols between the hierarchical levels. These > symbols can be a problem within XML files and would possibly need to be encoded with the string > (lower examples).

DataCite XML examples for GCMD Keywords are:

```
<subjects>
  <subject subjectIdentifier="14b19e68-0fb3-43b1-a102-537c4e33c338" subject-
    Scheme="GCMD Earth Science Keywords" schemeURI="https://fo-
    rum.earthdata.nasa.gov/app.php/tag/GCMD+Keywords">"EARTH SCIENCE > SOLID EARTH
    > GEODETICS > COORDINATE REFERENCE SYSTEM"
  </subject>
</subjects>

<subjects>
  <subject subjectScheme="GCMD Instruments">Earth Remote Sensing Instruments &gt;
    Passive Remote Sensing &gt; Positioning/Navigation</subject>
  <subject subjectScheme="GCMD Instruments">Earth Remote Sensing Instruments &gt;
    Passive Remote Sensing &gt; Positioning/Navigation &gt; GPS</subject>
  <subject subjectScheme="NASA/GCMD Earth Science Keywords">EARTH SCIENCE &gt; SOLID
    EARTH &gt; GEODETICS</subject>
</subjects>
```

The ELIS00ATA example includes:

```

<subjects>
  <subject xml:lang="en" subjectScheme="NASA/GCMD Earth Science Keywords"
    schemeURI="https://gcmd.earthdata.nasa.gov/kms/concepts/concept_scheme/sci-
    encekeywords/" classificationCode="5498572c-aaed-4c08-8aad-8b297057e9c">GEO-
    DETICS
  </subject>
  <subject xml:lang="en" subjectScheme="NASA/GCMD Earth Science Keywords"
    schemeURI="https://gcmd.earthdata.nasa.gov/kms/concepts/concept_scheme/sci-
    encekeywords/" classificationCode="48571017-0cc3-4ac7-b9ab-d0df8ed99a6c">RINEX
  </subject>
</subjects>

```

7 Contributor

All institutions and people involved in a sample’s workflow—from collection to archival (or discarding/destruction)—may be captured in the free-text `contributor` property. If `contributor` is used, the sub-properties `contributorName` and `contributorType` are mandatory.

Note that to be included in the reference to a resource, a person or organization must be listed in a `creator` property (and can then be additionally listed in a `contributor` property). People and organizations listed only in a `contributor` property are not included in the resource reference.

Potential contributors can be a local contact person/group as a contributor. This, however, could be information that is changing over time. The provision of a group with a generic email address is currently the favoured option. In contrast to creators, contributors are not included in the citation.

DataCite XML Example for ELIS00ATA:

```

<contributors>
  <contributor contributorType="ContactPerson">
    <contributorName>lastname, firstname</contributorName>
    <givenName>firstname</givenName>
    <familyName>lastname</familyName>
    <nameIdentifier schemeURI="https://orcid.org/" nameIdentifierScheme="OR-
    CID">0000-000x-xxxx-xxxx</nameIdentifier>
    <affiliation affiliationIdentifier="https://ror.org/00hjks330" affiliationIden-
    tifierScheme="ROR">Royal Observatory of Belgium</affiliation>
  </contributor>
  "add more contributors if necessary"
</contributors>

```

8 Date with 8a dateType

DataCite allows the provision of different dates relevant for the dataset or publication. These should be provided in the following format:

“YYYY, YYYY-MM-DD, YYYY-MM-DDThh:mm:ssTZD or any other format or level of granularity described in W3CDF². Use RKMS-ISO8601³ standard for depicting date ranges.

² <https://www.w3.org/TR/NOTE-datetime>

³ The standard is documented here: <http://www.ukoln.ac.uk/metadata/dcmi/collection-RKMS-ISO8601/>

Example: 2004-03-02/2005-06-02. Years before 0000 must be prefixed with a - sign, e.g., -0054 to indicate 55 BC.” (DataCite Metadata Schema 4.6, Documentation⁴)

The subproperty “dateType” must be used to specify a given date (**dateType is mandatory when “date” is used**). Allowed values for dateType from a controlled list are mainly related to text publications (i.e., submitted, accepted, copyrighted, etc.), some, however can be used also for research data: created, collected (defining the period of measurements), available (for embargoed data).

In the case of the ELIS00ATA station, it could be something like:

```
<dates>
  <date dateType="Collected" dateInformation="RINEX daily data collection: from 2009
    to nowadays">2009-02-13/</date>
  <date dateType="Updated" dateInformation="RINEX headers latest change">2022</date>
</dates>
```

12 RelatedIdentifier

Must be used for connecting stations to networks and vice versa. Can be used to link to format descriptions (RINEX, SINEX) or key publications. Some of the information (e.g., the link to format descriptions) could be “hard-coded” in all GNSS station metadata. The Summary Table in the Appendix provides recommendations on objects that should be included (cited) in the DataCite metadata as “RelatedIdentifier”

In the case of the ELIS00ATA station, it could be something like:

```
<relatedIdentifiers>
  <relatedIdentifier      relatedIdentifierType="DOI"      relationType="IsPartOf">10.24414/FST8-P256</relatedIdentifier> (connection to a GNSS Network)
  <relatedIdentifier      relatedIdentifierType="w3id"      relationType="IsSupplementedBy">https://w3id.org/moid/station.622722647c227b76eb0294e2</relatedIdentifier>
    (link to GNSS metadata in M3G)
  <relatedIdentifier      relatedIdentifierType="URL"      relationType="IsDocumentedBy">
    https://files.igs.org/pub/data/format/rinex_4.00.pdf</relatedIdentifier> (link to
    RINEX Format description Version 4.0)
</relatedIdentifiers>
```

16 Rights

This is an optional field, but we strongly recommend using it for the licence under which the data are distributed. Examples are following

```
<rightsList>
  <rights xml:lang="en" schemeURI="https://creativecommons.org/" [16] rightsIdentifierScheme="Creative Commons" rightsIdentifier="CC-BY-4.0"
    rightsURI="https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/">
</rightsList>

<rightsList>
  <rights xml:lang="en" rightsIdentifier="URL" rightsURI="https://science.data.nasa.gov/license/">
</rightsList>
```

⁴ <https://datacite-metadata-schema.readthedocs.io/en/4.6/properties/date/>

The information about the GNSS data license will be included in the upcoming version of GeodesyML thanks to the new property `<geo:license>` and the use of code list files (license-codelists.xml) maintained by IGS. The inclusion of specific terms from the eu-repo-Access-Terms vocabulary⁵ describing data access conditions will be discussed and possibly included in a future version of this document.

17 Description

The description has several sub-properties and we recommend to use at least `abstract`. This property shall briefly describe the resource and the context in which the resource was created. It is important for data discovery and is usually displayed in every data portal.

Example for the ELIS00ATA DOI metadata

```
<descriptions>
  <description xml:lang="en" descriptionType="Abstract">Permanent GNSS station dataset as
daily RINEX files</description>
</descriptions>
```

Example from "GNSS data of the global GFZ tracking network" <https://doi.org/10.5880/GFZ.1.1.2020.001>

```
<descriptions>
  <description xml:lang="en" descriptionType="Abstract"> Since the early 1990s, the GFZ has
operated a global GNSS station network with currently about 70 stations for precise satellite
clock & orbit determination, realization of the terrestrial reference frame, radio occultation
measurements or studies on crust dynamics. A subset of these stations contributes also to the
tracking networks of the International GNSS Service (IGS) and the EUREF Permanent GNSS Network
(EPN). Other stations contribute to GFZ observatories (IPOC, DESERVE, TERENO), to the GPS
Atmosphere Sounding Project (GASP), to WMO Global Climate Observing System Reference Upper-Air
Network (GRUAN) or to other external cooperations.
```

We offer data of 51 GFZ GNSS stations under this DOI. Nearly all stations are equipped with Javad or Septentrio hardware. Depending on the location and hardware they provide data of GPS (L1 / L2 / L5), GLONASS (L1 / L2 / L3), Galileo (E1 / E5a / E5b / E6), BeiDou (B1 / B2 / B3), QZSS (L1 / L2 / L5 / L6), NAVIC (L5), and SBAS (L1 / L5).

The GNSS Station Network Site (<https://isdc.gfz-potsdam.de/gnss-station-network/>) provides direct access to the 1s and 30s sampled RINEX data (near real-time, file based) and to real-time streams. Real-time streams are available for stations contributing to the IGS. Raw data GNSS binary raw observations are available upon request. All GFZ Stations follow the site guidelines of the International GNSS Service (<https://kb.igs.org/hc/en-us/articles/202011433-Current-IGS-Site-Guidelines>)

Station specific metadata can be found at our metadata portal SEMISYS. An overview of the list of stations with direct links to the station specific metadata in Semisys is available via ftp://datapub.gfz-potsdam.de/download/10.5880.GFZ.1.1.2020.001/2020-001_Ramatschi-et-al_List-of-GFZ-GNSS-Stations-with-links-to-SEMISYS.pdf. `</description>`

```
</descriptions>
```

⁵ https://guidelines.openaire.eu/en/latest/literature/field_accesslevel.html

18 GeoLocation

Very important, includes station coordinates, bounding box of Survey or global coverage. Coordinates must be provided with the following ranges: latitude = -90 to 90, longitude = -180 to 180! Examples are following – information can ideally be retrieved from Site Logs/GeodesyML

In the case of the ELIS00ATA geolocationPlace and geolocationPoint were included in the DOI metadata:

```
<geoLocations>
  <geolocation>
    <geolocationPlace>Utsteinen</geolocationPlace>
    <geolocationPoint>
      <pointLongitude>23.34632222</pointLongitude>
      <pointLatitude>-71.94670278</pointLatitude>
    </geolocationPoint>
  </geolocation>
  <geolocation>
    <geolocationPlace>ATA</geolocationPlace>
  </geolocation>
</geoLocations>
```

Example for GEOLOCATION BOX

```
</geoLocations>
  <geolocation>
    <geolocationBox>
      <westBoundLongitude>-70.2028</westBoundLongitude>
      <eastBoundLongitude>-69.1608</eastBoundLongitude>
      <southBoundLatitude>-22.8533</southBoundLatitude>
      <northBoundLatitude>-19.7611</northBoundLatitude>
    </geolocationBox>
  </geolocation>
</geoLocations>
```

This information can be extracted from the IGS site log and the GeodesyML file of ELIS00ATA:

Example: IGS site log

```
1. Site Location Information
City or Town           Utsteinen
State or Province      : N/A
Country                : Antarctica
Tectonic Plate         : ANTARCTIC
Approximate Position (ITRF)
  X coordinate (m)     : 1820674.651
  Y coordinate (m)     : 785852.011
  Z coordinate (m)     : -6043167.351
Latitude (N is +)     : -715648.14
Longitude (E is +)    : +0232046.76
Elevation (m,ellips.) : 1389.9
Additional Information  : (multiple lines)
```

Example GeodesyML file:

```

<geo:siteLocation>
  <geo:SiteLocation gml:id="site-location">
    <geo:city>Utsteinen</geo:city>
    <geo:state>N/A</geo:state>
    <geo:countryCodeISO codeSpace="urn:gnss-metadata.eu:country-code" codeL-
      ist="https://gnss-metadata.eu/geodesyml/codelists/country-codes-codelist.xml#Geode-
      syML_CountryCode" codeListValue="ATA"><![CDATA[ATA]]></geo:countryCodeISO>
  <geo:tectonicPlate codeSpace="urn:ga-gov-au:plate-type"><![CDATA[ANTARCTIC]]>
</geo:tectonicPlate>
  <geo:approximatePositionITRF>
    <geo:cartesianPosition>
      <gml:Point gml:id="itrf_cartesian">
        <gml:pos srsName="EPSG:7789"><![CDATA[1820674.6509791 785852.01079096 -
          6043167.3509294]]></gml:pos>
      </gml:Point>
    </geo:cartesianPosition>
    <geo:geodeticPosition>
      <gml:Point gml:id="itrf_geodetic">
        <gml:pos srsName="EPSG:4978"><![CDATA[-71.946704907813 23.346323170093
          1389.852]]></gml:pos>
      </gml:Point>
    </geo:geodeticPosition>
  </geo:approximatePositionITRF>
  <geo:notes></geo:notes>
</geo:SiteLocation>
</geo:siteLocation>

```

3. References

DataCite Metadata Working Group. (2021). DataCite Metadata Schema Documentation for the Publication and Citation of Research Data and Other Research Outputs v4.4. DataCite. <https://doi.org/10.14454/3W3Z-SA82>

Evans, P. L., A. Stollo, A. Clark, T. Ahern, R. Newman, J. F. Clinton, H. Pedersen, and C. Pequegnat (2015). Why seismic networks need digital object identifiers, *Eos*, 96, <https://doi.org/10.1029/2015EO036971>

International Federation of Digital Seismograph Networks. (2014, 2023). FDSN recommendations for seismic network DOIs and related FDSN services. <https://doi.org/10.7914/D11596>

Wilkinson, M. D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., Baak, A., Blomberg, N., Bouiten, J.-W., da Silva Santos, L. B., Bourne, P. E., Bouwman, J., Brookes, A. J., Clark, T., Crosas, M., Dillo, I., Dumon, O., Edmunds, S., Evelo, C. T., Finkers, R., ... Mons, B. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. In *Scientific Data* (Vol. 3, Issue 1). Springer Science and Business Media LLC. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

4. Appendix

4.1. Acronyms

FAIR Principles	Guiding Principles for research data management. Data shall be F indable, A ccessible, I nteroperable and R eusable (Wilkinson et al., 2016)
DOI	digital object identifier
PID	persistent identifier (globally unique and resolvable identifier to persons, institutions, digital objects, physical samples, instruments, etc.
RINEX	Receiver Independent Exchange Format (Link to documentation https://igs.org/formats-and-standards/)
Sinex	Solution (Software/Technique) Independent Exchange Format (https://www.iers.org/IERS/EN/Organization/AnalysisCoordinator/SinexFormat/sinex.html)
SKOS	Simple Knowledge Organization System, is a W3C recommendation that provides a way to represent vocabularies and taxonomies in a machine-readable format (https://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/).
Scholix	Scholarly Link Exchange, an initiative of the Research Data Alliance (RDA) and the World Data System (WDS) to improve linking between scholarly literature and research data (e.g., https://scholexplorer.openaire.eu/)

4.2. Overview on metadata content for different GNSS data types

DataCite property	subproperty	GNSS Station	GNSS Network	AC product series	ACC combined product series
Notes		Mapped from GeodesyML, Site logs as much as possible			
<i>identifier (M)</i>		DOI Code	DOI Code	DOI Code	DOI Code
<i>creator (M)</i>	ORCID, ROR	Institution responsible for the station	Institution, individuals (following institutional rules)	AC, individuals (following institutional rules)	IGS
<i>title (M), examples</i>			e.g., GNSS data of the global GFZ tracking network	e.g., CODE final product series for the IGS	
<i>publisher (M)</i>		DOI minting agency/ repository	DOI minting agency/ repository	DOI minting agency/ repository	
<i>publicationYear (M)</i>					
<i>resourceTypeGeneral (M)</i>		dataset	dataset	dataset	dataset
<i>resourceType (M)</i>		GNSS station data	GNSS network		
<i>subject (R)</i>	Scheme GCMD Science Keywords	EARTH SCIENCE > SOLID EARTH > GEODETICS	EARTH SCIENCE > SOLID EARTH > GEODETICS	EARTH SCIENCE > SOLID EARTH > GEODETICS	EARTH SCIENCE > SOLID EARTH > GEODETICS
	Scheme GCMD Science Keywords	EARTH SCIENCE SERVICES > DATA ANALYSIS AND VISUALIZATION > GLOBAL POSITIONING SYSTEMS	EARTH SCIENCE SERVICES > DATA ANALYSIS AND VISUALIZATION > GLOBAL POSITIONING SYSTEMS	EARTH SCIENCE SERVICES > DATA ANALYSIS AND VISUALIZATION > GLOBAL POSITIONING SYSTEMS	EARTH SCIENCE SERVICES > DATA ANALYSIS AND VISUALIZATION > GLOBAL POSITIONING SYSTEMS
	GCMD Platforms Earth Remote Sensing Instruments > Passive Remote Sensing > Positioning/Navigation >...	e.g., Beidou, GLONASS, GNSS, GPS, Galileo, NavIC QZSS, SBAS	e.g., Beidou, GLONASS, GNSS, GPS, Galileo, NavIC QZSS, SBAS	Beidou, GLONASS, GNSS, GPS, Galileo, NavIC QZSS, SBAS	Beidou, GLONASS, GNSS, GPS, Galileo, NavIC QZSS, SBAS
	Terms from IGS formats and standards	Add name from the IGS format description (https://igs.org/formats-and-standards), e.g., RINEX, Clock RINEX SINEX, SP3d			
	Free subjects	GNSS station data	GNSS network	IGS, International GNSS Service, AC product	IGS, International GNSS Service, final product

<i>contributor (R)</i>	ORCID, ROR	Contributing persons, observatories, institution	Pis with ORCID and ROR	AC with affiliation (and ROR)	All ACs, ACC staff (with ORCID and ROR)
<i>date (R)</i>	BeginDate/ EndDate or coverage	As defined in the data format description (https://igs.org/formats-and-standards) , dates must comply with the DataCite Schema definition (https://datacite-metadata-schema.readthedocs.io/en/4.6/properties/date/)			
	Available	Only for embargoed data	Only for embargoed data	Only for embargoed data	Only for embargoed data
<i>relatedIdentifier (R)</i>	Cites/ References	Add DOI to key publications or data reports	Add DOI to key publications or data reports	Add DOI to key publications or data reports	Add DOI to key publications or data reports
	IsPartOf/ HasPart IsDerivedFrom	Add DOI of the network or networks the station is contributing to (IsPartOf)	Add DOIs of stations contributing to the network (HasPart)	Add DOIs of stations contributing to the product (IsDerivedFrom)	Add DOIs of AC solutions contributing to the ACC products (IsDerivedFrom)
	Continues/ IsContinuedBy			Can be used to make the connection between ultra-rapid, rapid, final IGS solutions	
	IsDocumentedBy	add link/ DOI to the format description, use format names from https://igs.org/formats-and-standards			
<i>geoLocation (R)</i>	geoLocationPoint (R)	Station coordinates (lat/lon)			
	geoLocationBox (R)		Bounding box of network	Bounding box: global coverage (range: -180, 180, -90, 90)	
	geolocationPlace (O)	Name of location			
<i>rights (O)</i>		Optional property, but recommended: provide name and link to the licence under which the data are distributed. When the licence derives from a schema (e.g. Creative Commons), please add the rights subproperties as defined in https://datacite-metadata-schema.readthedocs.io/en/4.6/properties/rights/			
<i>description (O)</i>		Permanent GNSS station dataset as daily RINEX files	A brief description of the resource and the context in which the resource was created.		
Examples		https://doi.org/10.24414/ROB-GNSS-BRUX00BEL (ROB)	https://doi.org/10.5880/GFZ.1.1.2020.001 (GFZ)	https://doi.org/10.7892/boris.75876.1	

Download Global Change Master Directory (GCMD) keywords here: <https://qcmd.earthdata.nasa.gov/static/kms/> (RDF, JSON, XML, csv formats, static page)

GCMD Science keywords describe variables and observations, Platforms include satellite systems, Data Format derive from IGS definitions (<https://igs.org/formats-and-standards>)

Each metadata property must follow the definitions in the DataCite Schema (<https://datacite-metadata-schema.readthedocs.io/en/4.6/>).